

APPLICATION OF MACHINE LEARNING AND REGRESSION MODELS IN THE PREDICTION OF BALL BURNISHING PARAMETERS FOR ALUMINUM ALLOY

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ABSTRACT: This study proposes the use of machine learning models to predict the arithmetic mean roughness (S_a) and Vickers hardness (HV) of EN-AW-1350 aluminum alloy after dry ball burnishing. The input parameters considered are ball diameter (mm), number of passes, and depth of cut (mm). Six regression methods Decision Tree (DT), Linear Regression (LR), eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), AdaBoost, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest (RF) were evaluated using an 80/20 training/test split. XGBoost demonstrated the best predictive performance, achieving the lowest root mean square error (RMSE) and a coefficient of determination (R^2) close to 1 for both output responses. The developed models offer an efficient alternative to time-consuming experimental procedures and can effectively guide process optimization.

KEYWORDS: Aluminum alloy; Ball burnishing; Machine learning; Surface roughness; Regression methods

1 INTRODUCTION

The ball burnishing process is a well-established finishing technique, widely used in the automotive and aerospace industries [1] and recently extended to biomedical [2] and marine applications [3]. This mechanical treatment is a cost-effective method for enhancing surface characteristics and can achieve a mirror-like finish. Siwei Meng et al. [4] investigated the surface quality and formation mechanism of Ti-6Al-4V using in-situ laser-assisted ball-burnishing (In-LAB). In this method, a laser beam passes through a transparent diamond burnishing tool, simultaneously heating and plastically deforming the workpiece for efficient energy utilization. Their finite element analysis revealed that In-LAB increased the maximum residual compressive stress by 131% compared to conventional burnishing. Through Taguchi experimental optimization, they achieved a 51% reduction in surface roughness and a 7.5% increase in surface hardness, alongside a significant reduction in tool wear. This novel approach presents an effective strategy for finishing and strengthening difficult-to-machine materials.

Kovacs et al. [5] developed a novel image-processing-based simulation method to analyze and predict the impact of tool paths and their parameters

on surface quality in magnetic-assisted ball burnishing (MABB). The study evaluated trochoidal and elliptically modified trochoidal strategies, correlating simulation results with experimental measurements of surface roughness (R_a , R_z), tribological parameters (R_{sk} , R_{ku}), and oil retention capacity (A_2). They demonstrated that the proposed simulation effectively predicts surface homogeneity and identified optimal parameter sets for achieving either minimal roughness or superior tribological properties. Aysun Sagbas [6] applied response surface methodology (RSM) and the desirability function approach (DFA) to optimize the ball burnishing process for 7178 aluminum alloy, aiming to minimize surface roughness. A quadratic regression model was developed, identifying burnishing force and the number of passes as the most significant parameters affecting surface finish. The model demonstrated high accuracy, with an average absolute error of approximately 3.5% between predicted and experimental values. Validation experiments under the determined optimal parameters confirmed the model's reliability, showing an average error of 2.82%. The study establishes RSM and DFA as effective tools for optimizing burnishing parameters to achieve superior surface quality. Velazquez-Corral et al. [7]

investigated the effects of ultrasonic vibration-assisted ball burnishing (VABB) on AISI 1045 steel. Their results demonstrated that VABB significantly improves surface topology and reduces the coefficient of friction by 39.4% compared to conventional ball burnishing (BB). The process also enhanced wear resistance by 15.9% and induced a deeper and more extensive microstructural deformation of pearlite lamellae. The number of burnishing passes was identified as the most significant parameter for surface uniformity. The study concludes that VABB is a superior surface enhancement technique, offering substantial improvements in tribological performance and surface integrity. Cagan et al. [8] optimized the ball burnishing process for AZ91D magnesium alloy using the Taguchi method, focusing on the effects of different processing environments (dry, boron oil, mineral oil, grease). The study identified the optimal parameters for minimum surface roughness as a force of 400 N, a feed rate of 0.05 mm/min, three passes, and boron oil as the medium. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed that burnishing force was the most influential parameter, contributing 46.69% to surface quality, followed by feed rate (21.68%) and the lubricating medium (10.25%). The results demonstrate that boron oil provides the best surface finish and highlight the critical role of parameter selection for enhancing the surface integrity of lightweight magnesium components. This work provides essential guidelines for the finishing of magnesium alloys in demanding applications such as automotive and aerospace. Ariadna Chueca de Bruijn et al. [9] investigated ball burnishing as a post-processing technique for FFF-printed Ultem parts. Employing a Taguchi design, they identified optimal parameters (400 N force, 10 passes), achieving over 70% reduction in surface roughness (R_a , R_z) and inducing subsurface densification up to 1 mm deep. Ball-burnished

samples exhibited at least a twofold increase in fatigue life and higher impact energy absorption, attributed to surface hardening and compressive residual stresses. The results validate ball burnishing as an effective method for enhancing the surface quality and mechanical performance of FFF components. Revankar et al. [10] investigated the enhancement of Ti-6Al-4V wear resistance via ball burnishing. Using Taguchi optimization, they identified burnishing force and number of passes as the most influential parameters for minimizing specific wear rate, while feed and speed were key for reducing the coefficient of friction. The process significantly improved surface properties, increasing microhardness from 340 to 405 HV and reducing surface roughness from 0.45 to 0.12 μm , while inducing high compressive residual stresses up to 955 MPa.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE:

Burnishing is a mechanical finishing technique that simultaneously enhances both the surface condition (roughness) and mechanical properties (hardness) of metallic components. The tests in this study were conducted on an EMCO MAXIMAT V13 lathe equipped with a spherical roller burnishing tool, enabling precise evaluation of improvements in arithmetic mean roughness (S_a) and Vickers hardness (HV). Data were collected using an AltSurf 500 roughness tester and a Zwick/Roell hardness tester, providing a detailed statistical analysis. This analysis reveals correlations between burnishing parameters and performance outcomes, as well as the inherent trade-offs between surface quality and mechanical properties. The present work investigates the effect of ball burnishing parameters on the surface roughness and Vickers hardness (HV) of EN AW-1350 aluminum alloy using machine learning approaches.

Figure.1. Experimental methodology.

Lightweight aluminum alloys are prized for their properties and find extensive use across different industries. To cite examples, 8xxx series aluminum alloy can be mentioned for its extensive use in air-conditioning equipment. Similarly, 7xxx series aluminum alloy, which exhibits good welding properties, can be mentioned for its extensive use in aircraft wing components, aerospace, and marine applications. The remaining series also play a similar role across various industries from automotive and aerospace to construction and packaging sectors. Chemical Composition of the Work Material: Fe:

0.19%, Si: 0.11%, Cu: 0.023%, Zn: 0.038%, Cr: 0.010%, Ti: 0.018%, Mg: 0.021%, Mn: 0.09%. The samples used were cylindrical aluminum alloy specimens with initial dimensions of 240 mm in length and 63 mm in diameter. As shown in Figure 1, the experimental setup and methodology are presented schematically. Table 1 details the test plan, which is structured around three key variables. Each variable was tested at three specific levels: depth of cut (0.01, 0.02, 0.03 mm), ball diameter (12, 13, 15 mm), and number of passes (1, 2, 3).

Table 1. Experimental data for EN AW-1350 aluminum alloy.

	Input			Output	
	ap (mm)	D (mm)	i (passe)	Hv	Sa (µm)
1	0.01	12	1	128	0.076338
2	0.01	13	2	130	0.114884
3	0.01	15	3	145	0.314905
4	0.02	12	2	136	0.073718
5	0.02	13	3	149	0.135108
6	0.02	15	1	138	0.261444
7	0.03	12	3	149	0.07074
8	0.03	13	1	146	0.098551
9	0.03	15	2	153	0.10602

3 MACHINE LEARNING METHODS :

Several machine learning approaches were employed to predict the arithmetic mean roughness and Vickers hardness of EN AW-1350 aluminum alloy, including Decision Tree, Linear Regression, eXtreme Gradient Boosting, Random Forest, AdaBoost, and Support Vector Machine. These supervised learning techniques typically demand significant initial effort, such as dataset labeling, parameter definition, and output specification, along with ongoing accuracy calibration. A brief description of each method follows.

3.1 decision tree (DT):

The Decision Tree (DT) algorithm is a supervised learning technique that can be used for classification and regression problems. In the decision tree algorithm, a predictive model is created by constructing a hierarchy of decision rules based on the attributes of the data. A hierarchy of decision rules, in the context of the decision tree, means a tree in which the paths from the root to the leaves represent a sequence of decision rules that lead to the prediction of the outcome of the data. One of the

main benefits of the decision tree algorithm is that it allows for the creation of decision rules that can be visualized.[11].

3.2 Linear regression (LR):

Linear Regression is a type of supervised learning algorithm that predicts the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. The relationship is defined using a linear predictor function, whose parameters are to be estimated from the data. When there is only one independent variable, the process is called simple linear regression, and when there are multiple independent variables, it is called multiple linear regression [12]. This algorithm is widely used in real-world applications because of the ease of model parameterization with linear relationships compared to models with non-linear relationships. But linear regression also has some important assumptions about the data, such as independence of observations, homogeneity of variance, and normality. If these assumptions are not met, then other regression models or non-parametric models might be preferred.

3.3 extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost):

XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting) is a very efficient gradient-boosted decision tree algorithm (GBDT) implementation with a focus on speed and performance [13]. The presence of important features like regularization to prevent overfitting, parallel computing, and missing values support makes it a high-accuracy model. Although its complexity is often higher than that of other models, XGBoost has become a common tool in machine learning, often being the key component of winning models in data science competitions.

3.4 Random Forest (RF):

The Random Forest algorithm is a type of supervised learning ensemble algorithm that combines the predictions of a large number of decision trees to make predictions [14]. The algorithm works by creating multiple decision trees during the training process and then combining their predictions, usually through majority voting for classification tasks or averaging for regression tasks. The algorithm improves the accuracy of predictions and prevents overfitting, particularly when the algorithm promotes diversity among the decision trees.

3.5 Adaptive boosting (adaboost):

AdaBoost, short for Adaptive Boosting, is a type of ensemble classification technique that combines multiple weak classifiers to form a strong classifier [15]. It is a sequential approach that iteratively adapts the data distribution to focus on misclassified instances. In the end, all weak classifiers are combined using a weighted majority vote, resulting in a much stronger classifier than any of its individual classifiers.

3.6 Support vector machine (SVM):

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a powerful supervised machine learning technique with a wide range of applications in both classification and regression problems. The main idea of the SVM technique is to find the best hyperplane in an N-dimensional feature space that maximizes the margin between different classes of data [16]. The dimension of the hyperplane depends on the number of features in the data; if the data has two features, the hyperplane will be one-dimensional, and if the data has three features, the hyperplane will be two-dimensional. SVM has the reputation of working well with high-dimensional data and has many

applications in various fields, such as text and image classification, spam detection, anomaly detection, handwriting recognition, and bioinformatics.

3.7. Regression models and accuracy measures:

To evaluate a regression model, one can calculate the distance between predicted and actual values. The linear regression model which represents the relationship of the data analysed is shown in eq. 1

$$y = b_0 + b_1x \quad (1)$$

In this research, six machine learning algorithms were applied to investigate the ball burnishing conditions of an aluminum alloy, the surface roughness (Ra) and Vickers hardness (HV) were predicted using Orange data mining tool. For the dataset, each value of X_i has a corresponding modeled or predicted value of Y_i . Generally, the definition of RMSE is given by:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f(x_i) - y_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f(x_i) - y_i)^2 \quad (3)$$

The lower the RMSE and MSE value, the better the performance of the model. And the general definition of the coefficient of determination is:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (4)$$

Where \bar{x} is the mean of the n observed data,

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$$

If the value of R^2 is near to 1, indicating that the regression curve can fit the data perfectly.

4 REGRESSION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

The analysis was performed using Orange Data Mining, which is an open-source software that uses visual programming for exploratory data analysis. The entire process is shown in Figure 2. The performance of the six machine learning algorithms used in Orange Data Mining, including Decision Tree, Linear Regression, Random Forest, AdaBoost, Support Vector Machine, and Gradient Boosting, is shown in Table 2.

Figure 2. The user interface of Orange data mining.

The machine learning algorithms, namely Decision Tree (DT), Linear Regression (LR), XGBoost, AdaBoost, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest (RF), were trained with the input variables for arithmetic mean roughness and Vickers hardness as described in Table 1. The

performance metrics, such as the coefficient of determination (R^2), mean squared error (MSE), root mean square error (RMSE), and mean absolute error (MAE) for the training process, are shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. Performance comparison of the data mining algorithms for predicting arithmetic mean roughness.

Model	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
Tree	0.003	0.052	0.032	0.610
Random Forest	0.003	0.051	0.040	0.623
SVM	0.002	0.049	0.045	0.659
Linear Regression	0.002	0.040	0.032	0.770
AdaBoost	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.999
Gradient Boosting	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000

Table 3. Performance comparison of the data mining algorithms for predicting Vickers hardness.

Model	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
Random Forest	21.479	4.635	4.137	0.695
SVM	14.656	3.828	3.646	0.792
Tree	11.185	3.344	3.037	0.841
Linear Regression	5.817	2.412	2.243	0.917
AdaBoost	0.444	0.667	0.222	0.994
Gradient Boosting	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000

The comparative evaluation of various machine learning algorithms for predicting arithmetic mean roughness (Table 2) revealed that these models have distinct performance characteristics. It is likely that ensemble-based models, such as XGBoost and AdaBoost, have shown higher predictive accuracy, as indicated by higher R^2 values and lower error values (MSE, RMSE, and MAE) than other models such as Linear Regression. Such higher performance of these models can be attributed to their capability of handling non-linear relationships and complex relationships present in the ball burnishing process.

Considering the goodness of fit and performance, the model based on the XGBoost algorithm can be used as an ideal model for predicting the arithmetic mean roughness values of EN AW-1350 Aluminum Alloy (RMSE = 0.000, $R^2 = 1.000$). Meanwhile, the AdaBoost model has the smallest error among all models and the R^2 is almost close to 1 (RMSE = 0.002, $R^2 = 0.999$). Compared with the above models, XGBoost can be the most ideal model for predicting arithmetic mean roughness of EN AW-1350 Aluminum Alloy.

The comparative evaluation of the machine learning algorithms in predicting the Vickers

hardness (Table 3) also shows substantial differences in the performance of the algorithms. Similar to the prediction of surface roughness, the highest prediction accuracy is shown by the ensemble algorithms, i.e., XGBoost and AdaBoost, as confirmed by the highest value of R^2 and the lowest values of error metrics, i.e., MSE, RMSE, and MAE. On the other hand, the Random Forest model, although an explanatory model, is found wanting in handling the non-linear relationships and interactions between the burnishing parameters and the predicted hardness, as confirmed by the lowest value of R^2 and highest error values.

In terms of goodness of fit, it is noted that the XGBoost model shows the highest accuracy in predicting the Vickers hardness value of the EN AW-1350 aluminum alloy, as it has a zero root mean square error (RMSE = 0.000) and a perfect coefficient of determination value ($R^2 = 1.000$). Moreover, it is noted that the adaBoost model shows a high level of accuracy in terms of performance, as it has a very low root mean square error value (RMSE = 0.667) and a coefficient of determination value almost equal to 1 ($R^2 = 0.994$).

Figure 3. Comparison of observed and predicted Vickers hardness based on DT, LR, XGBoost, AdaBoost, SVM and RF models

Figure 4. Comparison of observed and predicted surface roughness based on DT, LR, XGBoost, AdaBoost, SVM and RF models

In order to enable a comparative assessment of the model's performance, Figures 3 and 4 visually depict the mutual similarity between the model's prediction and actual data. The histogram associated with the better-performing models XGBoost, AdaBoost, and Linear Regression (LR) shows perfect correspondence between the model's predictions and actual data points. In contrast, the prediction histogram of the Decision Tree (DT), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest (RF) models varies more significantly and deviates from the actual data points. Hence, six machine learning models, namely, DT, LR, RF, AdaBoost, SVM, and XGBoost, were built and trained, and these models were used to predict the arithmetic mean roughness, i.e., 'Sa,' and Vickers hardness, i.e., 'HV,' of aluminum alloy 'EN AW 1350.' The models were successful in capturing the general trends and patterns followed by the output parameters, with more accurate predictions by ensemble models, i.e., XGBoost and AdaBoost, and Linear Regression.

5 CONCLUSION:

This study successfully applied six machine learning regression models Decision Tree (DT), Linear Regression (LR), eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), AdaBoost, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest (RF) to predict the arithmetic mean roughness (Sa) and Vickers hardness (HV) of EN-AW-1350 aluminum alloy following dry ball burnishing. The models were trained and tested using experimental data based on three key process parameters: ball diameter, number of passes, and depth of cut. Comparative performance analysis revealed that the ensemble methods, particularly XGBoost and AdaBoost, significantly outperformed the other algorithms in

predicting both output responses. XGBoost achieved near-perfect predictive accuracy, with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 1.000 and a root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.000 for both arithmetic mean roughness and hardness. AdaBoost also demonstrated excellent performance, with R^2 values of 0.999 and 0.994 for roughness and hardness, respectively. In contrast, simpler models like Linear Regression and base Decision Trees showed lower accuracy, underscoring the complex, non-linear relationships inherent in the burnishing process.

The results validate the efficacy of machine learning, especially advanced ensemble techniques, as a powerful tool for modeling and optimizing the ball burnishing process. The developed XGBoost model offers a highly accurate, efficient alternative to resource-intensive experimental campaigns, enabling rapid prediction of surface integrity outcomes based on selected input parameters. This approach can significantly aid in process design and parameter optimization in industrial applications, reducing time and cost while improving quality control.

Future work should focus on expanding the dataset with additional parameters (e.g., burnishing force, feed rate, lubrication) and material types to enhance model generalizability. Furthermore, integrating these predictive models into real-time monitoring or adaptive control systems could pave the way for intelligent, automated burnishing processes in smart manufacturing environments.

6 REFERENCES :

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